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**GLOBAL TRENDS AND CHALLENGES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT:
IMPLICATIONS FOR UKRAINE**

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The rapid development of information technology, its total entry into human life inevitably creates new challenges and, at the same time, opens horizons for new opportunities for the education sector. Accordingly, today Ukraine faces the need to develop new approaches to the organization of the educational system in light of the requirements of the current state of human development: globalization, informatization, accelerating the pace of life.

The modern system of higher education, which fully meets the requirements of the time, is one of the main factors in increasing the quality of human capital, new ideas generator, a guarantee of dynamic development of the economy and society as a whole. In order for Ukrainian higher education to truly perform these important tasks effectively, it needs to be updated to take into account current global trends in the development of education in a broad socio-economic context.

This article aims to discuss and highlight current social, technological, financial, and academic trends in higher education institutions around the world to help students, educators and recruiters understand what changes to expect in the coming years.

We emphasize that globalization in education leads to an increase in academic mobility, the unification of curricula and teaching methods, as well as the widespread use of distance education.

Key words: higher education system of Ukraine; trends; educational technologies; reform; innovative technologies.

Introduction

The development of the modern Ukrainian state is characterized by integration processes. Ukraine is gradually adapting to the European educational space. Such integration requires European approaches to educational standards of educational content modernization, ensuring the quality of education.

Education is a unique social phenomenon that has a significant impact on all aspects of life and activity of the country, society, human civilization in general. In the modern scientific, technological and information revolution, education functions as a complex socio-economic organism that plays a major role in the social progress of mankind. It is one of the most important areas of labor and cognitive life.

The current stage of education system of Ukraine development is characterized by its reform, the search for ways to bring the content in line with the personal needs of students, world standards. Rapid development of information technology, its total entry into human life inevitably creates new challenges and, at the same time, opens horizons for new opportunities for the education sector. Accordingly, today Ukraine faces the need to develop new approaches to the organization of the educational system in light of the requirements of the current state of human development: globalization, informatization, accelerating the pace of life.

Also, in today's fast-paced information society, one of its main features is uncertainty. It, as noted by A. Tofler, as well as novelty and diversity causes deep apathy, which excludes millions of people from public life (Toffler, 2012, p. 396). Uncertainty causes shortcomings in planning in the higher education system, which is designed to be the driving force of society. Therefore, the analysis of modern educational and information technologies is important for understanding the trends that will determine the direction of higher education.

Analysis of the previous publications and researches

A thorough analysis of the material base on our topic shows that in foreign research the problems of higher education development have been studied in the following aspects: interdisciplinary trends in higher education (W.J. Jacob (Jacob, 2016), global trends in higher education (P.G. Altbach, L. Reisberg, L. E. Rumbley (Altbach, Reisberg, Rumbley, 2009)), trends in higher education in some regions and

countries (W.J. Jacob, J.N. Hawkins (Jacob, Hawkins, 2016) (China), trends that accelerate the introduction of technology in higher education (L. Johnson, A. Freeman, C. Hall (Johnson, Adams Becker, Estrada, Freeman, 2015)).

At the national level, the improvement and modernization of the higher education system is the responsibility of numerous government agencies, organizations and departments, among which the main ones are the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, the Department of Higher Education of MES of Ukraine, Committee of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine on Science and Education, National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine and others. They have developed and adopted numerous laws, government programs, charters, doctrines, concepts, strategies, principles and approaches to reforming higher education in Ukraine. The main scientific developments on the problems of reforming the system of higher education in Ukraine are the works of J. Bolyubash, M. Zgurovskiyi, V. Andrushchenko, M. Yevtukh, M. Stepko and other leading domestic scientists.

However, there is a need to analyze current global educational trends in order to determine the main trends in higher education in Ukraine.

Specifying the purpose of research

Therefore, the purpose of the article is to analyze the general features of modern trends and challenges in the process of higher education system development in the context of global and European integration processes and in case of emergency situations (e.g. Coronavirus pandemic).

Presentation of the main research material

The study examines the trends and challenges in the development of higher education in modern conditions. We emphasize that globalization in education leads to an increase in academic mobility, unification of curricula and teaching methods, and the widespread use of remote education. In the current conditions, the main task of education in the 3rd decade of XXI century, is the high use of new information technologies in the dissemination of knowledge, including the use of different distance learning methods.

The education system of society must meet its strategic objectives. The National Doctrine of Education Development in Ukraine emphasizes that education should become a strategic resource for improving the well-being of people, ensuring national interests, strengthening the authority and competitiveness of the state in the international arena (Stratehiiia rozvytku vyshchoi osvity Ukrainy..., 2020). However, the state of affairs in the field of education, the pace and depth of transformation do not fully meet the needs of the individual, society and the state. Globalization, change of technologies, transition to information technology society,

assertion of priorities of sustainable development, other features of modern civilization determine human development as the main goal, a key indicator and the main level of modern progress, the need for radical modernization of the industry; set before the state, society the task of ensuring the priority of the development of education and science, the priority of solving their urgent problems.

The modern system of higher education, which fully meets the requirements of the time, is one of the main factors in increasing the quality of human capital, new ideas generator, a guarantee of dynamic development of the economy and society as a whole. In order for Ukrainian higher education to truly perform these important tasks effectively, it needs to be updated to take into account current global trends in the development of education in a broad socio-economic context.

Higher education modernization in Ukraine requires overcoming a number of problems, among which the most pressing are:

- inconsistency of the training structure with the real needs of the economy;
- declining education quality;
- isolation from research field;
- slow integration into European and world intellectual space.

Experts also point to the significant expansion of the higher education system that has taken place in Ukraine since the Soviet Union period, implying both an increase in the number of higher education institutions and a rapid increase in the total number of students and university graduates. Problems such as the vocational education system collapse, skilled workers' shortage, the inability of many university graduates to find work in their specialty, educational and professional standards inflation, the excessive workload on teachers and insufficient funding of universities, growing levels of corruption in universities and others.

Such scientists as P. G. Altbach, L. Reisberg, L. E. Rumbley (Altbach, Reisberg, Rumbley, 2009) define the following main vectors of higher education development: new technologies, concern for quality, the struggle for the essence of higher education, the professionalization of higher education management and leadership. Regarding the first trend, researchers note that the impact of information and communication technologies can be seen in the exchange of knowledge through e-mail, blogs, wikis and podcasts, in the rapid spread of remote education and electronic publications of scientific journals and books, and to some extent in higher education management.

We think that the main step and idea in this process is to transform the approach to teaching and learning, which does not mean replacing traditional universities or traditional teaching methods. However, there is a huge difference in

how different countries can integrate new technologies. The state of development of

higher education in developing countries depends on the speed of closing the “digital divide”. We strongly believe that according to this statement quality will continue to be a high priority for higher education, and that the next step is the need to move towards mutual recognition and trust so that national quality assurance programs are internationally valid. Despite more than a decade of formalizing quality assurance programs, many elements of quality measurement and monitoring remain problematic.

The trend towards the professionalization of higher education management and leadership is due to the fact that higher education institutions are becoming larger and more important for society and individuals. Academic institutions and systems are beginning to collect data on themselves for use in policy development and refinement, as there is a growing need for complete and accurate regional and international data for analysis. Higher education is simply too large, complex and central to manage without data and professionalism.

W.J. Jacob, highlighting trends in higher education through the prism of an interdisciplinary approach, notes that this approach to research and teaching is important in order to best respond to the dynamic needs of today's higher education students (Jacob, 2016). He claims that there is now an increase in the number of interdisciplinary research among graduate students in many areas of study.

Among the main trends, we also single out the increase and diversification of courses and degrees and the emergence of hybrid means of educational material delivery, which is rapidly becoming a world standard in higher education. Mass open online courses bring new dynamics to learning, because they often include students from many different specialties, as well as students who do not have a degree. There is also an increase in cooperation between universities. Joint training and certification programs organized at different universities are now seen as more realistic or acceptable in today's technological context than in the past.

Changes in higher education trends can be traced in detail using NMC Horizon's higher education reports. Over almost nine years of research on key technological developments that will have a significant impact on the development of the education system worldwide, NMC (The New Media Centres) has identified trends, acute problems and major advances in technology or techniques that are likely to become widespread. in the relevant sector in the next five years.

The reports highlight the following key trends that accelerate the introduction of technology in higher education: solutions for blended learning, emphasis on quantitative assessment of learning, improving the culture of innovation, redevelopment of learning spaces, deeper learning, collective approach to learning,

evolution of online learning, rethinking the role of teachers, dissemination of open educational resources, rethinking the methods of educational institutions, cooperation between institutions, students in the role of creators, flexible approach to transformation, universal access to social networks, mixing formal and non-formal learning, decentralized support of information technology,

The solution of different complex problems depends primarily on the purposeful, scientifically sound activities of higher education teachers who have scientific knowledge of the theory and methods of vocational education.

At the same time, the modernization of higher education in Ukraine requires taking into account the general trends in the development of higher education systems in the context of globalization and European integration processes. Within the reforms in the field of higher education, which are taking place in the West, we can identify certain trends that are constantly developing in Ukrainian higher educational establishments.

Trends in higher education system development:

- public perception of universities as platforms for innovation and modern technologies. Experts insist that university management should encourage a creative approach to learning, as well as encourage the development of entrepreneurial elements in their structure;

- increasing the intensity of cooperation between universities, which is to pool their resources and coordinate actions to achieve common goals, including providing a more accessible, cheaper, and better quality of education. Even today, there are successful examples of such cooperation: a joint project of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts and University of Informatics and Arts, Lodz, Poland, Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts and Apsley Business School in London;

- development of the science of analysis and processing of large data sets. Today, companies operating in the consumer sector are constantly collecting data on the tastes and preferences of their customers. Similarly, this approach can be applied in the market of educational services;

- a combination of new and traditional learning formats, which led to the formation and development of a "blended learning" model;

- the priority of universal values and humanistic orientation;

- intensification of public and state efforts to bring education to the level of international standards and achievements in this field;

- formation of national-patriotic morality;

- development of education based on the newest psychological and pedagogical technologies;

- departure from the principles of authoritarian, ideological pedagogy, levelling the natural individual characteristics of all students;

– radical restructuring of education management through its democratization, decentralization, creation of regional management systems of educational institutions;

– development of non-state forms of ownership of educational institutions.

These most general tendencies in the education of Ukraine give rise to the corresponding derivative tendencies in all its subsystems: organizational-administrative, scientific, educational, upbringing, special-pedagogical, professional-technical, etc. They, reflecting the general problems of education in Ukraine, at the same time are specific due to the peculiarities and conditions of their activities.

The most significant trends that characterize the functioning of high schools in modern conditions are: 1) the desire to expand the variability of the content of the educational program, a certain profiling if necessary to comply with state standards of education; 2) efforts of educational institutions management to create complexes, united by a common strategic educational goal and traditional ties, following the general goal of building the organization and methodology of the learning process; 3) competition of general educational institutions of different types and forms of ownership based on the improvement of educational services,

According to the above-mentioned trends, we want to emphasize that the main principle of the reform is the democratization of education. In the study we have formulated the following principles:

– education universality;

– education continuity;

– unity and differentiation;

– replacement of narrow-profile education with broad-based;

– the principle of comprehensive student development;

– education through practice and labour broad front of education and upbringing, flexibility, statehood, socialization, science, and economics of education.

Each of these principles is relevant to any education. First of all, we can distinguish the principle of continuity, associated with the absence of obstacles in the transition from one educational institution to another and the consistency of curricula and programs, the development of professional orientation; the principle of continuity - universal availability of forms and means of education, replacement of narrow-profile training with a broad profile - promotes rapid retraining of employees and mobility in personnel policy; the principle of education through work and for work – involves filling the entire educational process with labour issues, professional knowledge, and skills that correspond to the stage and standard education.

Selected trends provide development opportunities and accelerate the process of modernization of higher education and harmonization of its content with the needs of modern society. After all, the evolution of technology affects society and it requires from education adequate strategies to train the younger generation. Global trends, directly and indirectly, affect education policy in Ukraine.

Currently, the international concept of educational services in Ukraine has led to an increase in the number of educational institutions and institutions (providers), which in turn has led to a diversification of expectations and needs of those wishing to receive an education. The development of the education system in the country requires additional income and new channels to obtain it. All this (increase in educational service providers, diversification of educational needs, and lack of funding) raises concerns about ensuring the quality of education and discrediting it. This trend will continue, as many people today want to acquire professional skills quickly and inexpensively, which can be done by providers of non-formal and informal education. But only higher education institutions with a long history and culture of teaching and educating the younger generation can form a comprehensively developed person, a bearer of the nation's cultural and intellectual traditions.

Higher education should prepare young people for professional activity in conditions of uncertainty and variability. This task requires politicians, HEI leaders, and teachers to reconsider the structure of traditional training programs, as well as to transform the pedagogy of the past, traditional approaches to teaching to new ones that are more in line with the conditions of the modern information society.

Conclusions

It is important to pay attention to key trends that accelerate the introduction of educational technologies in higher education, including new solutions for blended learning, improving the culture of innovation, the need for redevelopment of learning spaces, methods of deeper learning, renewing a collective approach to learning, open educational resources, cooperation between institutions of higher education; the application of the international practice of the concept of educational services in Ukraine leads to increased competition in this area, in particular in terms of retraining, which should encourage free economic education to implement and diversify formal and non-formal education programs to maintain and consolidate free economic education services.

Taking these trends into account in the planning of higher education institutions will contribute to their stable development and progress of higher education in Ukraine, integration into the world educational space and overcoming the consequences of uneven distribution of human capital, which will allow the country to take full advantage of new educational and information technologies.

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ГЛОБАЛЬНІ ТЕНДЕНЦІЇ І ВИКЛИКИ РОЗВИТКУ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ: НАСЛІДКИ ДЛЯ УКРАЇНИ

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Стрімкий розвиток інформаційних технологій, їх повне входження в життя суспільства та громадськості неминує створює нові виклики і одночасно відкриває горизонти для інноваційних і сучасних можливостей в освітній галузі. Відповідно, нині Україна стикається з необхідністю вироблення нових підходів до організації освітньої системи з урахуванням вимог сучасного стану людського розвитку: глобалізації, інформатизації, прискорення темпу життя.

Новітня система вищої освіти, яка абсолютно співпадає з вимогами часу, є базовим фактором підвищення якості людського капіталу, рушієм сучасних ідей, генератором стрімкого та потужного розвитку економіки та суспільства в цілому. Задля ефективності виконання важливих завдань, українську вищу освіту потрібно оновити з урахуванням сучасних світових тенденцій розвитку освіти у широкому соціально-економічному контексті.

Ця стаття має на меті обговорити та висвітлити сучасні соціальні, технологічні, фінансові та академічні тенденції у вищих навчальних закладах по всьому світу, щоб допомогти студентам, викладачам і рекрутерам зрозуміти, яких змін очікувати в найближчі роки.

Ми наголошуємо, що глобалізація в освіті веде до збільшення академічної мобільності, уніфікації навчальних планів та методів навчання, а також широкого використання дистанційної освіти.

Ключові слова: система вищої освіти України; тенденції; освітні технології; реформа; інноваційні технології.

МИРОВЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И ВЫЗОВЫ РАЗВИТИЮ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ: ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ ДЛЯ УКРАИНЫ

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Стремительное развитие информационных технологий, их полное вхождение в жизнь общества и общественности неизбежно создает новые вызовы и одновременно открывает горизонты для инновационных и современных возможностей в сфере образования. Соответственно, сегодня Украина сталкивается с необходимостью выработки новых подходов к организации образовательной системы с учетом требований современного состояния человеческого развития: глобализации, информатизации, ускорение темпа жизни.

Новейшая система высшего образования, которая абсолютно совпадает с требованиями времени, является базовым фактором повышения качества человеческого капитала, двигателем современных идей, генератором стремительного и мощного развития экономики и общества в целом. Для эффективности выполнения важных задач, украинское высшее образование нужно обновить с учетом современных мировых тенденций развития образования в широком социально-экономическом контексте.

Эта статья имеет целью обсудить и осветить современные социальные, технологические, финансовые и академические тенденции в высших учебных заведениях по всему миру, чтобы помочь студентам, преподавателям и рекрутерам понять, каких изменений ожидать в ближайшие годы.

Мы подчеркиваем, что глобализация в образовании ведет к увеличению академической мобильности, унификации учебных планов и методов обучения, а также широкого использования дистанционного образования.

Ключевые слова: система высшего образования Украины; тенденции; образовательные технологии; реформа; инновационные технологии.